

Rac-4h

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-16-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1206
Vial:	56	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 16 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/6/2021 3:26:42 PM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:54:44 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.841	4557830	50.40	363358
2	10.333	4486296	49.60	207185

Asy-4h

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-17-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	17	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 17
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/6/2021 4:10:03 PM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:53:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.855	11037328	96.85	875580
2	10.364	359187	3.15	16842